

PEOPLE AND AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS

EXPLORING NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS AND RESTORATION MEASURES IN FLOODPLAINS

TEACHING PROTOCOL

TYPE OF LESSON: STEM workshop

GRADE LEVEL: Secondary school

LESSON STRUCTURE: 1 School lesson (45 min) for the introduction (“Engage”),
2 Lessons (90 min) for the field diagnosis – ideally outdoors (“Explore”)
1 Lesson (45 min) for linking Problems & Restoration Measures (“Explain”)
1-2 Lessons (50-90 min) for designing the Wetland Action Plan (“Elaborate”)
1 Lesson (45 min) for games & reflection (“Evaluate”)

INTRODUCTION:

This learning unit aims to help students understand the importance of restoration measures and Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in the Danube and its floodplains.

The Danube River and its floodplains have historically been extensively modified through straightening, channelization, construction of dikes, removal of vegetation, simplified substrates, and the spread of invasive species. These changes disrupt natural processes, harming biodiversity, reducing flood protection, and limiting ecosystem services to humans. Nature-based solutions (NbS) use natural processes and ecological functions to restore degraded environments while providing benefits for people and nature. In this lesson, students will investigate these pressures, discover the science behind restoration strategies, and take part in hands-on activities to understand why NbS are essential for healthy rivers and for people’s well-being.

LEARNING OBJECTIVES:

By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- 1 Identify the main **pressures** on rivers and floodplains and their ecological impacts.
- 2 Explain how **restoration measures** and nature-based solutions (NbS) improve river and floodplain health.
- 3 **Compare** traditional grey solutions with mixed and nature-based solutions.
- 4 **Apply** NbS concepts to a real or simulated wetland site.
- 5 Develop a realistic **restoration plan** that balances ecology and human needs.
- 6 **Reflect** on trade-offs and future outcomes of different solutions.
- 7 Strengthen their **personal connection** and **sense of responsibility** toward wetlands.

KEYWORDS: Renaturierung / revitalisierung, Nature-based Solutions (NbS), longitudinal connectivity, lateral connectivity, straightening / channelization, invasive species, floodplain restoration, ecosystem resilience

TEACHING FRAMEWORK BASED ON THE 5E INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL

1. ENGAGE - Sparking curiosity

AIM: The purpose of this is to spark curiosity and activate prior knowledge by visually contrasting a degraded and a restored stretch of the Danube or other river, encouraging students to observe differences, raise questions, and begin reflecting on the links between river structure, biodiversity, and human experience.

ACTIVITY 1: SPOT THE DIFFERENCE

Show two contrasting images of the Danube or another river:

- i) One straightened and channelized stretch with artificially stabilized banks.
- ii) One restored floodplain with meanders, riparian forest, and backwaters.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which differences do you see?
- Which place do you think hosts more animals and plants? Why?
- Which would you prefer to visit?

ACTIVITY 2: EXPLORE THE RESTORE4LIFE INTERACTIVE VISUALIZATION

Students explore the *PEOPLE AND AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS ONLINE INTERACTIVE VISUALIZATION*. This activity invites them to observe key features, compare natural and altered river landscapes, and reflect on how restoration benefits both people and nature.

KEYWORDS / VOCABULARY: river channel; floodplain; meander; dyke; channelization; riparian zone; connectivity; ecosystem; restoration; Nature-based Solution (NbS)

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Guide students toward recognizing structural diversity, connectivity, and vegetation as indicators of ecosystem health. Online interactive visualization for *PEOPLE AND AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS RESTORE4LIFE EDUCATIONAL TOPIC*.

2. EXPLORE – Hands-on learning activity

AIM:

The purpose of this stage is to guide students in closely observing a real wetland or river section in order to recognize signs of human pressures and alterations. By documenting features such as river course, connectivity, bank vegetation, substrate, aquatic plants, and invasive species, students practice using ecological vocabulary and begin to build an evidence-based understanding of how these conditions influence biodiversity and ecosystem health. This hands-on diagnosis encourages inquiry, comparison, and curiosity about what a more natural river-floodplain system should look like.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Is the river straightened or meandering?
- Are the floodplains connected to the river, or blocked by dikes/roads?
- Which vegetation do you see along the riverbanks – is it dense, missing, or dominated by invasive species?
- How does the riverbed look – uniform, or with a mix of stones, gravel, dead wood, and microhabitats?
- What kinds of aquatic plants are present – too few, too many, or balanced?
- Can you find signs of invasive species? If yes, which ones?
- How do you think these conditions affect animals, plants, and people who live nearby?

KEYWORDS / VOCABULARY:

sinuosity; channelization; connectivity; longitudinal connectivity; lateral connectivity; floodplain; riparian vegetation; riverbank stability; substrate; epifauna; aquatic vegetation; invasive species; habitat diversity; erosion.

TEACHER SUPPORT:

In this phase students observe a local wetland/stream. If no field visit is possible, use the provided photos or diagrams.

If a field visit is possible, the teacher selects a safe and accessible site near the river where students can record observations directly in the **NBS WORKSHEET PART 1 (OBSERVATION & DIAGNOSIS)**. If fieldwork is not feasible, the teacher can provide high-quality photos, diagrams of river stretches showing contrasting conditions.

To deepen understanding, the **"R4L_Exploring the Habitat of a Stream" worksheet** can also be used as supplementary support, guiding students in identifying human alteration of the sinuosity of a watercourse, connectivity, the structure of the river bank, bank vegetation, and substrate diversity. Teachers should encourage students to share findings in small groups, prompting comparisons and discussions with guiding questions, and helping them link observed pressures to their ecological consequences.

3. EXPLAIN – Making sense of the experiences

AIM:

The aim of this stage is to help students make sense of their observations by introducing the concepts of grey, mixed, and Nature-based Solutions for river and floodplain restoration. By comparing different types of human interventions to the river and floodplain and their impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human needs, students build a scientific understanding of why certain strategies are more sustainable than others. This stage links their field diagnosis to ecological processes and restoration science.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How do grey, mixed, and nature-based solutions differ from each other?
- Which type of measure improves biodiversity the most?
- Which type of measure offers the best long-term benefits for people (flood safety, recreation, clean water)?
- Which challenges arise when deciding between engineering measures and Nature-based restoration approaches?
- Why might a Nature-based Solution sometimes be more challenging to implement, but more beneficial in the long run?

KEYWORDS / VOCABULARY:

Grey solutions; Mixed (hybrid) solutions; Nature-Based Solutions (NbS); Connectivity (longitudinal, lateral); River morphology (sinuosity, depth, substrate); Ecosystem services (flood protection, biodiversity, water purification); Restoration measures (fish ladders, re-meandering, floodplain reconnection, riparian vegetation).

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Use the **NBS Worksheet (Part 2 – Possible Solutions)** to let students explore intervention options for each challenge.
- Provide students with **illustrated cards** showing Grey, Mixed, and NbS options to stimulate group dialogue and evaluation.
- Use short case studies or photo examples of Danube or another river restoration projects to illustrate real-world applications.
- Summarize with a class discussion highlighting why NbS are preferred in modern restoration science, but also acknowledge contexts where hybrid approaches are necessary.

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW

- 1 Students compare Grey, Mixed, and NbS approaches for different river challenges using illustrated cards and the worksheet.
- 2 In small groups, they discuss which measures are most effective for biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being.
- 3 The class then comes together for a teacher-led explanation, linking measures to ecological concepts (connectivity, substrate diversity, riparian vegetation).
- 4 Real-world photos or case studies are used to anchor the discussion in authentic Danube restoration practice.

4. EXTEND / ELABORATE – Expanding understanding

AIM: The aim of this stage is to empower students to apply their knowledge by designing a realistic plan for improving a wetland or river stretch. Building on their field diagnosis and understanding of possible restoration measures, students now think creatively and critically about how Nature-based Solution approaches can be implemented, which require cooperation with authorities or landowners, and which can involve the local community. This activity encourages systems thinking, teamwork, and ownership by showing students that even small contributions—such as planting native vegetation, monitoring habitats, or raising awareness—can play a role in larger restoration strategies.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- What are the main ecological problems that we have identified in this wetland/river section?
- What would a healthy, natural wetland look like here?
- What are the societal problems that Nature-based Solutions could realistically address in this area?
- Who should be involved in making these measures happen (students, community, landowners, authorities)?
- Which NbS approaches would bring the biggest benefit for biodiversity?
- Which NbS approaches would help most with flood protection and people's safety?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Facilitate group work by reminding students of their observations from *PART 1 (DIAGNOSIS)* and their solution choices from *PART 2 (EXPLAIN)* of the worksheet.
- Encourage students to balance ideal solutions with realistic feasibility, helping them identify which actions are suitable for community efforts and which require institutional involvement.
- Use examples from real-world Danube/another river restoration projects to inspire ideas and demonstrate that local actions can link to broader basin-wide strategies.
- Support students in presenting their plans (posters, storyboards, or oral presentations) and ensure that all groups reflect on both ecological and social aspects.

MATERIALS NEEDED:

- 1 **NBS Worksheet (Part 3 - Wetland Action Plan)**
- 2 Flipchart paper, sticky notes, and markers for group posters or storyboards
- 3 **Illustrated cards** and photos of NbS measures for inspiration
- 4 Optional: digital tools (PowerPoint, online whiteboard)
- 5 Examples of Danube or other/local restoration case studies

5. EVALUATE – Testing knowledge through games

AIM: This stage allows students to consolidate and test their understanding of NbS approaches and multifunctional floodplains by engaging in interactive games. By playing digital or project-developed games, they can explore real-world challenges, apply what they have learned, and reflect on the effectiveness of different strategies.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which strategies worked best in the game for both nature and people?
- How did NbS approaches perform compared to grey or mixed approaches?
- What trade-offs/compromises did you notice when choosing different measures?
- What role did stakeholders (e.g., government, communities, engineers, ecologists) play in the implementation of these approaches?
- What did you learn from the game that you could apply to real floodplain restoration?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Choose an appropriate game (e.g., *Stop Disasters!*, *Flood Resilience Game*, *Rivercraft 2*, or *R4L* project-developed tools).
- Brief students on the aim of the game and the link to their previous activities (diagnosis, solutions, action plan).
- Facilitate group play or individual sessions, ensuring that all students understand the rules.
- Encourage note-taking during gameplay to support later reflection.
- Lead a debrief discussion where groups share their experiences and connect game outcomes to the real-world NbS framework and Danube floodplains.
- Use the games as an assessment tool: observe whether students can apply key concepts and vocabulary in their explanations.

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DESIGNING MEASURES FOR A NATURE-BASED SOLUTION FOR OUR WETLAND

WORKSHEET 1. EXPLORE – OBSERVE & DIAGNOSE TABLE

FIELD WORK: Try to answer the question below by observing the respective features in the wetland/stream section in front of you!

FEATURE TO OBSERVE	DESCRIBE WHAT DO YOU SEE?	NATURAL / ALTERED?
River course (straight / meandering)		
Floodplain connection (open / blocked by dike / road)		
Riverbank vegetation (dense / missing / invasive)		
Channel depth & shape (varied / uniform)		
Substrate (sand, gravel, stones, dead wood)		
Aquatic vegetation (too little / balanced / too much)		
Signs of invasive species? (yes / no, which ones?)		

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

DESIGNING MEASURES FOR A NATURE-BASED SOLUTION FOR OUR WETLAND

WORKSHEET 2. POSSIBLE MEASURES FOR HUMAN PRESSURES ON RIVERS (EXPLAIN)

PURPOSE OF THE ACTIVITY

This interactive **matching game** enables students to visually explore which **restoration measures**—with varying degrees of orientation toward nature (**Grey**, **Mixed**, and **Nature-Based Solutions [NbS]**)—can be applied to address common human **pressures on rivers and floodplains**.

The game provides an overview of these types of measures and motivates students to compare them and discuss their applicability depending on the available space for restoration.

By the end of the activity, students will better understand how **engineering** and **ecological restoration** approaches can be applied in a targeted way to restore functional rivers and floodplains, supporting **biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being**.

OVERVIEW OF THE GAME

Students work in small groups to:

- 1 Identify the main types of human pressures affecting rivers and floodplains.
- 2 Match them with the corresponding potential restoration measures from the three categories (Grey, Mixed, NbS).
- 3 Compare and discuss which measures are most effective, realistic, and beneficial for nature and people under different environmental conditions (e.g., available space for restoration, rural vs. urban setting, mountain vs. lowland stream).

The game can be played at two difficulty levels (see below).

STEP 1 – PREPARING THE GAME MATERIALS

Print pages 3-10 double-sided (flip on short edge) on four sheets of paper.

o Cut out the cards along their outlines:

Pressures – red outline (round)

Grey measures – grey outline (rectangle)

Mixed (Hybrid) measures – yellow outline (rectangle)

Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) – green outline (rectangle)

You will now have a complete set of **36 illustrated cards** showing the pressures and their possible measures, with an **image on the front** and the **title and description on the reverse side**.

Print **pages 11-19** single-sided on nine sheets of paper. These contain boxes with colored outlines and descriptions structured for the different human pressures and their corresponding measures.

STEP 2 – PLAYING THE GAME (GUIDED MATCHING)

- Place the worksheets (pages 11-19) on a table so that all group members can see them.
- Students take the cut-out cards with Grey, Mixed, and NbS restoration measures one by one and match them—based on the image—to the corresponding pressure and measure description on the worksheets.
- They can check whether they correctly matched the image and description by reading the text on the **back of the card**, which should correspond to what is written on the worksheet.
- During and after matching, groups discuss which **restoration solution type** would be most appropriate to mitigate each human pressure under various environmental conditions (e.g., space availability, rural vs. urban setting, mountain vs. lowland stream) and which provides the greatest benefits for **nature and people**.

FOR A MORE ADVANCED VERSION:

Students are encouraged to look carefully at the illustrations, identify them, and place them in the correct positions on the worksheets **without reading the descriptions** (either on the worksheet or on the back of the cards).

Print double-sided: GREY MEASURES

GREY MEASURES

CONCRETE BARRIERS

on the river bottom (bottom sills) or riprap reinforcements to stabilize incision and prevent lateral erosion

Ⓒ

CONTROLLED SPILLWAYS

for occasional technical flooding of floodplains and polders

Ⓑ

CONCRETE FISH PASSES

technical fish ladders designed only for certain species, often ineffective for weaker swimmers

Ⓐ

SINGLE-SPECIES PLANTING

incl. con-native species (e.g. hybrid black poplar) with low ecological value; mowed grass strips along river banks

Ⓕ

VEGETATED GABIONS

Riprap armouring of river banks can be replaced by vegetated gabions (wire cages filled with stones). Longitudinal low wooden or stone dams create littoral shallow habitats protected from ship-induced wave impact

Ⓔ

UNIFORM SUBSTRATE

Streambed with uniform substrate

Ⓓ

WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANTS

Construction of wastewater treatment plants with advanced removal of inorganic nutrients and trace chemicals

Ⓘ

LARGE-SCALE MECHANICAL REMOVAL

(dredging, cutting); laborious fishing or collection of invasive animals; poisoning of entire water bodies

Ⓗ

COMPLETE MECHANICAL HARVESTING

or dredging to remove excess plants from the water body and the banks

Ⓖ

MIXED APPROACH

ECO-ENGINEERED GROYNES/ FLOW DEFLECTORS

from wood or stone reduce flow velocity and creating some habitat diversity

Ⓒ

RESTORATION OF OXBOW LAKES AND SIDE-ARMS

by re-opening blocked inlets/
outlets in order to link the river
again with water bodies in the
floodplain

Ⓑ

BYPASS FISH MIGRATION CHANNELS

with semi-natural design and
gentle slope enable migration of
most fish species around barriers,
additionally offering small resting
or even reproduction habitats for
aquatic life

Ⓐ

PLANTED NARROW ROWS OF NATIVE TREE

or shrubs along stabilized river
banks, or buffer strips with some
shrubs for some shading of the
river

Ⓕ

FASCINES / WILLOW MATTRASSES

River banks fixed through biotechnical
engineering with fascines (live willow
bundles layered with stones) or willow
brush mattresses, strips of reed, grass
or shrubs

Ⓔ

PLACEMENT OF NATURAL ROCKS

and addition of stones supporting
flow and sediment heterogeneity

Ⓓ

BUFFER STRIPS COMBINED WITH RETENTION BASINS

to capture polluted runoff from
agriculture, roads and settlements;
Additional treatment steps (e.g., treatment
wetlands) added to wastewater treatment
plants as final polishing step; Green roofs
and permeable pavements in cities
to reduce diffuse pollution

Ⓘ

TARGETED MANUAL REMOVAL OF INVASIVE SPECIES IN HOTSPOTS

Prevent artificial warming of rivers from
sewage water input and power stations
by cooling of sewage with heat pumps;
Management and disinfection of ballast
water from ships in ports; No fish stocking
from other catchment areas

Ⓗ

MANUAL REMOVAL OF EXCESS SPECIES

Targeted manual removal of excess
species from hotspots of growth,
while other parts of vegetation
remain as refuge for biota

Ⓖ

Print double-sided: NATURE-BASED SOLUTION MEASURES (NBS)

NATURE-BASED SOLUTION MEASURES (NBS)

REMOVING ARTIFICIAL EMBANKMENTS

enables lateral erosion, wideing of the river channel and re-meandering; artificial sediment addition , supports raising of the river bed, sediment dynamics and habitat diversity.

Ⓒ

RELOCATING OR REMOVING DYKES

Restoring full lateral connectivity of rivers and floodplains by relocating or removing dykes.

Ⓑ

ROCK RAMPS

may replace weirs and small dams, enabling full fish migration and sediment transport. However, barriers should be fully removed and rivers re-meandered wherever possible.

Ⓐ

RESTORING WIDE RIPARIAN BUFFER ZONES

with self-regenerating diverse native trees, shrubs and herbs structured by the natural zonation of vegetation in floodplains

Ⓕ

FULL REMOVAL OF RIVER BANK ARMOURING

and restoration of natural riverbank slopes, allowing natural erosion and deposition to shape banks dynamically. Establishment of a dynamic river corridor also serving as a buffer strip

Ⓔ

REINTRODUCTION OF LARGE WOODY DEBRIS

large natural stones or rocks, allowing natural erosion/deposition processes to rebuild habitat mosaic.

Ⓓ

RESTORING FLOODPLAINS AND WETLANDS AS NATURAL WIDE BUFFER STRIPS

between intensely used areas and water bodies; Re-meandering rivers to enhance natural self purification within the water body

Ⓘ

MINIMIZING HUMAN IMPACTS THAT SUPPORT INVASIVES

No artificial habitats, such as bank protection using rock fill or damming rivers for hydroelectric power

Ⓗ

RE-ESTABLISHING RIPARIAN BUFFER STRIPS

Prevent excessive nutrient input and vegetation growth via re-establishing riparian buffer strips to reduce nutrient inflow and to shade the water body, also contributing to instream habitat diversity

Ⓖ

PRESSURE

Rivers are often straightened, dredged and narrowed, leading to bed erosion (incision). This results in deep, uniform river channels with high flow velocity and low habitat diversity that drain waters from adjacent floodplains, with increased risks of sudden and high flood waves

Ⓒ

Lateral barriers such as embankments and dikes (levees) disrupt the lateral exchange between rivers and their floodplains. They hinder lateral movements of water, sediment, and fish (e.g. for reproduction), affecting riparian habitats and reducing vital ecosystem services.

Ⓑ

Barriers such as dams, weirs, culverts, sluices, and fords interrupt the longitudinal continuity of rivers. They obstruct the natural flow of water and sediment and block the migration of aquatic organisms.

Ⓐ

When natural riverbank vegetation such as trees, shrubs, and grasses is removed or degraded, erosion risk increases and rivers lose shading, cooling, and leaf litter inputs. This increases water temperature in summer, diminishes biodiversity, and affects water quality regulation.

Ⓕ

River banks armoured by rip-rap stones or concrete prevent natural erosion and sedimentation processes, and greatly reduce habitat diversity.

Ⓔ

Artificial or homogenized riverbeds (e.g., concrete-lined, dredged, or filled with uniform stones) provide few habitats for streambed organisms and fish. The absence of diverse habitats disrupts food webs, decreases biodiversity, and lowers ecological resilience.

Ⓓ

Domestic waste water, fertilizer, pesticides, heavy metals, and other pollutants from agriculture, industry, and urban runoff degrade water quality, cause eutrophication, harm aquatic life, and reduce the ecological and recreational value of floodplains.

Ⓘ

Invasive species displace or feed on native plants and animals, disrupt food webs, and thus alter river and floodplain ecosystems. They often spread rapidly when natural habitats are disturbed.

Ⓗ

High nutrient inputs cause the (excessive) growth of microalgae, macroalgae or macrophytes leading to oxygen depletion when vegetation decomposes, thus affecting all aquatic biota.

Ⓙ

LOSSES OF CONNECTIVITY

1

LONGITUDINAL CONNECTIVITY:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Barriers such as dams, weirs, culverts, sluices, and fords interrupt the longitudinal continuity of rivers. They obstruct the natural flow of water and sediment and block the migration of aquatic organisms.

(A)

CONCRETE FISH PASSES

technical fish ladders designed only for certain species, often ineffective for weaker swimmers

(A)

BYPASS FISH MIGRATION CHANNELS

with semi-natural design and gentle slope enable migration of most fish species around barriers, additionally offering small resting or even reproduction habitats for aquatic life

(A)

ROCK RAMPS

may replace weirs and small dams, enabling full fish migration and sediment transport. However, barriers should be fully removed and rivers re-meandered wherever possible.

(A)

LOSSES OF CONNECTIVITY

2

LATERAL CONNECTIVITY:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Lateral barriers such as embankments and dikes (levees) disrupt the lateral exchange between rivers and their floodplains. They hinder lateral movements of water, sediment, and fish (e.g. for reproduction), affecting riparian habitats and reducing vital ecosystem services.

ⓑ

CONTROLLED SPILLWAYS

for occasional technical flooding of floodplains and polders

ⓑ

RESTORATION OF OXBOW LAKES AND SIDE-ARMS

by re-opening blocked inlets/outlets in order to link the river again with water bodies in the floodplain

ⓑ

RELOCATING OR REMOVING DIKES

Restoring full lateral connectivity of rivers and floodplains by relocating or removing dykes.

ⓑ

ALTERATION OF RIVER HYDROMORPHOLOGY

3

CHANNEL STRAIGHTENING, NARROWING AND INCISION:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Rivers are often straightened, dredged and narrowed, leading to bed erosion (incision). This results in deep, uniform river channels with high flow velocity and low habitat diversity that drain waters from adjacent floodplains, with increased risks of sudden and high flood waves

©

CONCRETE BARRIERS

on the river bottom (bottom sills) or riprap reinforcements to stabilize incision and prevent lateral erosion

©

ECO-ENGINEERED GROYNES/ FLOW DEFLECTORS

from wood or stone reduce flow velocity and create some habitat diversity

©

REMOVING ARTIFICIAL EMBANKMENTS

enables lateral erosion, widening of the river channel and re-meandering; artificial sediment addition, supports raising of the river bed, sediment dynamics and habitat diversity.

©

ALTERATION OF RIVER HYDROMORPHOLOGY

4

ARTIFICIAL RIVER BEDS (INSTREAM HABITAT):

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Artificial or homogenized riverbeds (e.g., concrete-lined, dredged, or filled with uniform stones) provide few habitats for streambed organisms and fish. The absence of diverse habitats disrupts food webs, decreases biodiversity, and lowers ecological resilience.

Ⓓ

UNIFORM SUBSTRATE

Streambed with uniform substrate

Ⓓ

PLACEMENT OF NATURAL ROCKS

and addition of stones supporting flow and sediment heterogeneity

Ⓓ

REINTRODUCTION OF LARGE WOODY DEBRIS

large natural stones or rocks, allowing natural erosion/deposition processes to rebuild habitat mosaic.

Ⓓ

RIVER BANKS AND RIPARIAN ZONE PRESSURES

5

ARTIFICIALLY STABILIZED RIVER BANKS:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

River banks armoured by rip-rap stones or concrete prevent natural erosion and sedimentation processes, and much reduce habitat diversity.

Ⓔ

VEGETATED GABIONS

Riprap armoring of river banks can be replaced by vegetated gabions (wire cages filled with stones). Longitudinal low wooden or stone dams create littoral shallow habitats protected from ship-induced wave impact

Ⓔ

FASCINES / WILLOW MATTRESSES

River banks fixed through biotechnical engineering with fascines (live willow bundles layered with stones) or willow brush mattresses, strips of reed, grass or shrubs

Ⓔ

FULL REMOVAL OF RIVER BANK ARMOURING

and restoration of natural riverbank slopes, allowing natural erosion and deposition to shape banks dynamically. Establishment of a dynamic river corridor also serving as a buffer strip

Ⓔ

RIVER BANKS AND RIPARIAN ZONE PRESSURES

6

LOSS OF RIPARIAN VEGETATION AND SHADING:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

When natural riverbank vegetation such as trees, shrubs, and grasses is removed or degraded, erosion risk increases and rivers lose shading, cooling, and leaf litter inputs. This increases water temperature in summer, diminishes biodiversity, and affects water quality regulation.

Ⓕ

SINGLE-SPECIES PLANTING

incl. con-native species (e.g. hybrid black poplar) with low ecological value; mowed grass strips along river banks

Ⓕ

PLANTED NARROW ROWS OF NATIVE TREE

or shrubs along stabilized river banks, or buffer strips with some shrubs for some shading of the river

Ⓕ

RESTORING WIDE RIPARIAN BUFFER ZONES

with self-regenerating diverse native trees, shrubs and herbs structured by the natural zonation of vegetation in floodplains

Ⓕ

BIOLOGICAL/ECOLOGICAL PRESSURES

7

EUTROPHICATION:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Excessive inputs of nutrients cause excessive growth of microalgae, macroalgae or macrophytes leading to oxygen depletion when vegetation decomposes, thus affecting all aquatic biota.

©

COMPLETE MECHANICAL HARVESTING

or dredging to remove excess plants from the water body and the banks

©

MANUAL REMOVAL OF EXCESS SPECIES

Targeted manual removal of excess species from hotspots of growth, while other parts of vegetation remain as refuge for biota

©

RE-ESTABLISHING RIPARIAN BUFFER STRIPS

Prevent excessive nutrient input and vegetation growth via re-establishing riparian buffer strips to reduce nutrient inflow and to shade the water body, also contributing to instream habitat diversity

©

BIOLOGICAL/ECOLOGICAL PRESSURES

8

INVASIVE SPECIES:

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Invasive species displace or feed on native plants and animals, disrupt food webs, and thus alter river and floodplain ecosystems. They often spread rapidly when natural habitats are disturbed.

(H)

LARGE-SCALE MECHANICAL REMOVAL

(dredging, cutting); laborious fishing or collection of invasive animals; poisoning of entire water bodies

(H)

TARGETED MANUAL REMOVAL OF INVASIVE SPECIES IN HOTSPOTS

Prevent artificial warming of rivers from sewage water input and power stations by cooling of sewage with heat pumps; Management and disinfection of ballast water from ships in ports; No fish stocking from other catchment areas

(H)

MINIMIZING HUMAN IMPACTS THAT SUPPORT INVASIVES

No artificial habitats, such as bank protection using rock fill or damming rivers for hydroelectric power

(H)

CHEMICAL POLLUTION

9

CHEMICAL POLLUTION

Look carefully at the illustrations and match the pressure with its Grey, Mixed (Hybrid), and Nature-Based Solution (NbS) cards.

Place the cards in the correct boxes and discuss in your group which measures are most effective for nature and people.

Domestic waste water, fertilizer, pesticides, heavy metals, and other pollutants from agriculture, industry, and urban runoff degrade water quality, cause eutrophication, harm aquatic life, and reduce the ecological and recreational value of floodplains.

①

WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANTS

Construction of wastewater treatment plants with advanced removal of inorganic nutrients and trace chemicals

①

BUFFER STRIPS COMBINED WITH RETENTION BASINS

to capture polluted runoff from agriculture, roads and settlements; Additional treatment steps (e.g., treatment wetlands) added to wastewater treatment plants as final polishing step; Green roofs and permeable pavements in cities to reduce diffuse pollution

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RESTORING FLOODPLAINS AND WETLANDS AS NATURAL WIDE BUFFER STRIPS

between intensely used areas and water bodies; Re-meandering rivers to enhance natural self purification within the water body

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DESIGNING MEASURES FOR A NATURE-BASED SOLUTION FOR OUR WETLAND

WORKSHEET 3. OUR WETLAND RESTORATION ACTION PLAN - GROUP HANDOUT – STEP 4 (ELABORATE)

Work in groups to design your own wetland restoration plan. Discuss each box together, shortly write down which ideas you have developed, and maybe illustrate them by drawing simple sketches. Be creative and realistic — think about problems, wishes/goals, solutions, and what you can do as students.

OUR CHALLENGE	OUR WISH/GOAL	OUR ACTION PLAN – WHICH MEASURES ARE REALISTIC HERE?	NEXT STEPS
<p>Write down the main problems we discovered in this river/wetland.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which human pressures did we identify (e.g., channel straightening, invasive species, pollution)? • How do these pressures affect plants, animals, and people? 	<p>Imagine the perfect future for this wetland.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What would a healthy, natural wetland look like here? • Which animals, plants, or features should return? • How would people enjoy or benefit from it? 	<p>Decide on the restoration measures we could apply.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) would help? • Which actions are realistic for our site? • Which measures would require support from authorities, landowners, or the community? 	<p>Think : What can we students do about this now.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planting trees, starting a monitoring or awareness campaign, or an art project? • How can we involve our school, families, or community? • Which personal small steps can make a difference this year?